

Overview of scissor-type, bi-stable deployable structures

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Abstract

The term “deployable structures” encompasses a broad category of prefabricated structures that can be transformed from a closed compact configuration to a predetermined, expanded form, in which they are stable and can carry loads. The interest in deployable structures is due to the advantages they offer compared to conventional, non-deployable structures for certain types of applications, particularly in the temporary construction industry and the aerospace industry. For such applications, their potential for compact storage, transportability and easy erection and dismantling is of primary importance, and outweighs the restrictions imposed by the need for complex design and detailing, which are necessary to achieve deployability. In this paper an overview of scissor-type deployable structures exhibiting snap-through (bi-stable) behavior during deployment are presented. In order to highlight the role of geometric incompatibility in the intensity of snap-through taking place during deployment and in the resulting stiffness of the deployed structure, two examples of simple structures exhibiting snap-through are presented first. Challenges, opportunities and limitations of this type of deployable structures are discussed, aiming at providing useful insights and directions for current and future researchers in this field.

Keywords: deployable structures, transformability, scissor-type elements, snap-through, bi-stable structures

1. Introduction

The term deployable structures is used for prefabricated structures that can be transformed from a closed compact configuration to a predetermined, expanded one, in which they are stable and can carry loads. Thus, deployable structures can adapt their shape, mechanical and physical properties and their overall behavior to the external excitations and the requirements associated with their use at different phases in their life. For certain applications, mainly in the temporary construction industry and the aerospace industry the potential of deployable structures for compact storage, transportability, and easy erection and dismantling is very useful. Several conferences (Bulson [1], Escrig and Brebbia [2], Pellegrino and Guest [3]), special issues of technical journals (Pellegrino [4]) and books (Gantes [5]) have been devoted to the study of deployable structures. Interest in such structures continues and several new researchers are now active in the field, for example Akgün et al. [6], Chen and Feng [7], van Knippenberg et al. [8], Roovers and De Temmerman [9], Veuve et al. [10].

Deployable structures can be classified into several categories according to different criteria. Depending on the environment of application, we differentiate between structures that are used on the earth as opposed to others which are deployed in space. Depending on the type of structural members there are strut structures where the basic modules are 1-D bars, or surface structures, which consist of 2-D building modules. Strut structures can be further classified into groups, on the basis of their structural behavior. Some of them, called manually locking deployable structures, behave as structural mechanisms during deployment, and need the addition of new members in order to be stable in the deployed configuration. Other designs, the so-called bi-stable or self-locking deployable structures, are stable and stress-free in the folded and in the deployed configuration, except for dead weight effects.

During deployment, however, geometric incompatibilities cause the development of second order strains and stresses. Hence, the structural response is geometrically nonlinear and is characterized by a snap-through type of behavior that ‘locks’ the structure and assures its stability in the deployed configuration. Such structures were introduced by Zeigler [11], developed by Krishnapillai and Zalewski [12], investigated in-depth by Gantes (for example [13]) and are now further explored by Arnouts [14]. This latter type of deployable structures is addressed in the present paper.

2. Snap-through: the concept and simple examples

The term snap-through is used in structural mechanics to denote the sudden transition of a structural system from one geometric configuration to another, different shape. An illustrative example from everyday life is what may happen to an umbrella in windy days, as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Snap-through of umbrella due to wind

2.1. Example 1: von Mises truss

The simple, symmetric, 2-bar truss illustrated in Figure 2 is one of the most commonly used examples for describing snap-through in quantitative terms. This is actually a three-hinge truss with span $2L$ and height H , subjected to a concentrated vertical load at its crown (for example, Livanou and Gantes [15]).

Figure 2: Geometry and loading of von Mises truss

By enforcing equilibrium, compatibility and constitutive conditions in the deformed configuration, shown in dotted blue line in Figure 2, we end up with the following equilibrium equation (1), relating applied load P to resulting vertical displacement δ at the crown, plotted in Figure 3.

$$\frac{P}{EA} = 2 \left[1 - \frac{\sqrt{\left(\frac{L}{H}\right)^2 + \left(1 - \frac{\delta}{H}\right)^2}}{\left(\frac{L}{H}\right)^2 + 1} \right] \frac{1 - \frac{\delta}{H}}{\sqrt{\left(\frac{L}{H}\right)^2 + \left(1 - \frac{\delta}{H}\right)^2}} \quad (1)$$

Successive deformed configurations, corresponding to characteristic points along the equilibrium path of Figure 3, are plotted with black line in Figure 4, whereas green lines denote the undeformed configuration and dotted green lines the mirror position of the undeformed configuration with respect to the horizontal plane at the level of supports. Due to the applied load the crown displaces vertically, which causes shortening and compression in the bars. Smaller inclination of the bars in the deformed configuration results in gradually diminishing stiffness up to the limit point B, corresponding to the ultimate load P_u , characterized by zero stiffness. This is followed by a branch of negative stiffness, with zero load at point C, where the horizontal truss bars cannot resist any vertical load. Beyond point C there is reversal of load, a second limit point D with zero stiffness and then a branch of positive stiffness up to the mirror configuration E, in which the bars have their original length, hence they have

no axial force and provide zero vertical resultant force. Beyond E the bars are elongated and act in tension, thus the behavior is stable and the stiffness increases constantly. The equilibrium path can be traced in its entirety if displacement control is employed. For load control the path is followed from A to B and then snap-through occurs, and the truss deforms to point F. This is actually a dynamic process and the structure oscillates around F, eventually coming to rest due to friction.

Figure 3: Equilibrium path of von Mises truss

Figure 4: Successive deformed configurations of von Mises truss

In the above it is assumed that the material remains elastic and that the compressive axial force in the two bars remains below Euler buckling levels. In actual cases, these conditions may only be fulfilled if the height to span ($H/2L$) ratio is low, so that the geometric incompatibility is smaller and the intensity of snap-through is softer. However, this is then associated with much lower structural stiffness and strength of the truss. This is illustrated in Figure 5, where equilibrium paths for $H/2L$ ranging between 0.05 and 0.20 are plotted. The decisive influence of the height to span ratio on the structural characteristics is evident. This is further quantified in Figure 6, where the intensity of the ultimate load P_u is plotted as a function of $H/2L$.

Figure 5: Equilibrium paths of von Mises truss for different values of height to span ratio

Figure 6: Ultimate load of von Mises truss as a function of height to span ratio

2.2. Example 2: three-hinge truss

The possibility of occurrence of member buckling during the process of global deformation associated with snap-through can be illustrated for the example of Figure 7, which is actually a more realistic variation of the von Mises truss, in which the two bars have been replaced by trusses.

Figure 7: Geometry and loading of three-hinge truss

The equilibrium path has been obtained from a geometrically nonlinear finite element analysis and is shown in Figure 8 with solid red line, while the corresponding theoretical path (neglecting member buckling) is also plotted with dotted blue line. Elastic material behavior has been assumed. Corresponding deformed shapes at characteristic points are shown in Figure 9. As shown from the difference in deformation between points A and B, bifurcation takes place due to local member buckling of the lower truss chords between joints, causing initiation of a descending equilibrium branch before reaching the theoretical limit point. From the deformed configuration at point C it is observed that this is then combined with global buckling of each truss, in order to accommodate geometric incompatibility.

Figure 8: Equilibrium path of three-hinge truss

Figure 9: Successive deformed configurations of three-hinge truss

3. Bi-stable scissor-type deployable structures

The snap-through concept described above has been transferred to scissor-type deployable structures through the efforts by several researchers, with Zeigler, Krishnapillai and Gantes having played a pivotal role.

3.1. Geometric layout

These structures consist of so-called scissor-like elements (SLEs) (Figure 10), pairs of bars connected to each other at an intermediate point through a pivotal connection which allows them to rotate freely about an axis perpendicular to their common plane but restrains all other degrees of freedom, while, at the same time, their end points are hinged to the end points of other SLEs. Several SLEs are connected to each other to form units with plan views of regular polygons (Figure 11). The sides and radii of the polygons are SLEs. These polygons, in turn, are linked in appropriate arrangements constituting deployable structures, which are either flat or curved in their final deployed configuration (Figure 12).

Figure 10: Scissor-like-element

Figure 11: Typical polygonal units consisting of scissor-like-elements

Figure 12: Typical flat and curved scissor-type deployable structures

3.2. Structural aspects

A fundamental design requirement of the snap-through type deployable structures is that they are self-standing and stress-free both in their fully closed and in their fully deployed configurations. This is enforced by proper geometric design, requiring straightness of the members in these two states, preferably accounting for joint size and eccentricities, for better accuracy. During deployment, however, geometric incompatibilities cause the development of second order strains and stresses. Hence, the structural response is geometrically nonlinear and is characterized by a snap-through type of behavior that ‘locks’ the structure and assures its stability in the deployed configuration. This is illustrated by the experimental equilibrium path of the deployment of a typical polygonal unit, shown in Figure 13. The level of geometric incompatibility is influenced by the geometric design of radial scissor-like-elements and can be adjusted by proper selection of geometry parameters. In addition to geometry, the intensity of snap-through depends also on material and cross-section characteristics of inner SLEs. Stronger snap-through is associated with increased danger of member failure during deployment, which may be either due to member buckling or due to material yielding, and are obviously undesirable, as they will reduce the subsequent bearing capacity of the structure in its deployed configuration under service loads.

Figure 13: Test of scissor-unit and corresponding equilibrium path

On the other hand, the strict geometric requirements to achieve deployability, as well as the inherent low stiffness of SLEs due to their pivotal connections, lead to low stiffness and strength of deployed structures. From that point of view, stronger snap-through is desirable, as it will result in a stiffer deployed structure.

3.3. Design challenges

As a direct consequence of the structural behavior in the two distinct phases in the life of such structures, during deployment and in the deployed configuration, the main design challenge is how to balance the conflicting requirements during these two phases. Stronger geometric incompatibility is beneficial for the service phase, as it will lead to stiffer structures, that are more likely to satisfy verification criteria in ultimate and serviceability limit states. However, such stronger geometric incompatibility may cause undesirable failures during deployment, as the high resulting axial forces and bending moments in members of inner SLEs may cause material yielding and/or inelastic member buckling.

This is illustrated schematically in Figure 14. In the left part of this figure, a compromise between low and high incompatibility leads to a feasible design space, where all requirements are satisfied. There may be cases, however, where such design space does not exist and the design is not feasible, as shown in the right part of Figure 14. This is mostly the case for larger external load demands, as this is a factor involved only in design requirements in service. On the other hand, parameters such as span, material and member sections, and geometric lay-out, affect the response in both phases, but in an opposite manner. It is hence deduced that this type of structures are more likely to provide viable solutions in cases of low external load demands.

Figure 14: Schematic representation of balancing conflicting design requirements during deployment and under service loads

4. Conclusion

In structural engineering snap-through buckling is considered a potential failure mode that may be critical for very flexible, “shallow” structures, such as arches or domes. It is associated with large deformations leading structures to a substantially different configuration, which is in general undesirable for conventional constructions. This is therefore considered as a destructive phenomenon.

However, the deployable structures presented here make use of snap-through buckling in a constructive manner. In this case each of the two distinct geometric configuration serves a meaningful purpose, namely the folded configuration is suitable for storage and transportation, while the deployed one for service conditions. Moreover, snap-through buckling is exploited as a form of prestressing, thus providing stiffness to the deployed structure, which therefore does not need additional members for stabilization.

The challenge in the design of such structures for real-size, architectural applications is to balance between lower geometric incompatibility, which is desirable during deployment in order to avoid inelastic member buckling, and higher one that would be preferable for having adequate stiffness and strength of the deployed structure. Optimizing between these conflicting requirements is an interesting objective for future research in this field. As of now, feasible design solutions have been found only for cases of very low design loads, such as for indoor applications.

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